

Handling of research data

Checklist for planning and description of handling of research data in research projects

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This checklist should assist you to describe key aspects of the handling of research data in a structured manner and to identify the resources and competence required for implementation. Please use section 2.4 of your application to comment on the topics mentioned below.

Research data includes measurement data, laboratory values, audiovisual information, texts, survey or observation data, methodological test procedures and questionnaires. Compilations, software and simulations can equally represent a central result of scientific research and are therefore also included under the term research data. Research data in some subject areas is based on the analysis of objects (such as tissue, material, rock, water and soil samples, test specimens, installations, artefacts and art objects), so its handling must be just as careful and consideration must be given to a technically adequate option for subsequent reuse whenever meaningful and possible. Should subsequent reuse of the resulting research data be closely associated with objects, then please also elaborate on this by providing all relevant information.

Please consider the existing standards in your discipline, any current subject-specific recommendations and any existing infrastructure services (such as data repositories, archives or collections). An overview of existing structures is available in the RIsources research infrastructure portal (https://risources.dfg.de/home_en.html) and the re3data registry of research data repositories (<http://re3data.org>).

Further information on this topic and subject-specific recommendations are available via: www.dfg.de/research_data/checklist

Checklist Regarding the Handling of Research Data

1. Data description

How does your project generate new data? Is existing data reused? Which data types (in terms of data formats like image data, text data or measurement data) arise in your project and in what way are they further processed? To what extent do these arise or what is the anticipated data volume?

2. Documentation and data quality

What approaches are being taken to describe the data in a comprehensible manner (such as the use of available metadata, documentation standards or ontologies)? What measures are being adopted to ensure high data quality? Are quality controls in place and if so, how do they operate? Which digital methods and tools (e.g. software) are required to use the data?

3. Storage and technical archiving the project

How is the data to be stored and archived throughout the project duration? What is in place to secure sensitive data throughout the project duration (access and usage rights)?

4. Legal obligations and conditions

What are the legal specifics associated with the handling of research data in your project? Do you anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility? What is in place to consider aspects of use and copyright law as well as ownership issues? Are there any significant research codes or professional standards to be taken into account?

5. Data exchange and long-term data accessibility

Which data sets are especially suitable for use in other contexts? Which criteria are used to select research data to make it available for subsequent use by others? Are you planning to archive your data in a suitable infrastructure? If so, how and where? Are there any retention periods? When is the research data available for use by third parties?

6. Responsibilities and resources

Who is responsible for adequate handling of the research data (description of roles and responsibilities within the project)? Which resources (costs; time or other) are required to implement adequate handling of research data within the project? Who is responsible for curating the data once the project has ended?